

PEDAGOGICAL DISPUTES AND WAYS TO SOLVE THEM EFFECTIVELY

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Abstract. *This article highlights the main conflicts of pedagogy, the methods of understanding and explanation between students and students, the great experience of an excellent pedagogue, and the relationship between a teacher and a student.*

Keywords: *manners, correct education, culture of treatment, dedication, honesty, beauty, justice.*

"Education is our future, it is a matter of life and death. Therefore, we have no right to delay reforms in this area. No matter how complicated it is, we must lay the foundations of school education today. Because We lost time."

Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

INTRODUCTION. The practical action of a teacher as a specialist in the search for measures to prevent and eliminate negative pedagogical conflicts represents his work on himself. As a leader of young people, a teacher-educator should literally ensure the full performance of his creative duties in schools and form a pedagogical orientation. Conflict is considered one of the important events in the pedagogical process.

A conflict is a clash of opposing, incompatible forces, a conflict that represents a lack of mutual agreement between two or more parties, a conflict of interests.

Pedagogical conflict is a conflict of interests between a pedagogue and a student, parents, colleagues, or management in the pedagogical process. A pedagogue should be well-educated, mentally, morally, spiritually, have a wide range of knowledge, be fluent in speech, and possess pedagogical knowledge and skills. Pedagogical skills of the teacher are evident mainly in classroom and auditorium activities. A lively language, exchange of ideas, sincere attitude, respect, cooperation between the teacher and the pupil, students are necessary to achieve the main goal. How many children there are in his group, the teacher should study the character, family environment, psychology, behavior, knowledge level, achievements and shortcomings of each of them, and then he should know how to approach each child accordingly. There are different types of children in the groups. Each of them will have its own character. The teacher should study each child and get to know them individually. Some children are capable, mature and active in all aspects, some are weak and incompetent, and some are energetic. The main task of the group leader is to organize the educational influence on the children in the group assigned to him. The head of the class should have a comprehensive approach to students. The head of the class cooperates with the parents and deals with the education of the children, their level of education, their morals, achievements and shortcomings. If the teacher pays attention to these, it will eliminate the conflict between the teacher and the student. There should be contact, i.e. distance, between the student and the teacher. The student should be respectful towards the teacher. Conflict science is closely related to the sciences of pedagogy, psychology, and mology, spirituality, and sociology, and

works in cooperation with these sciences. Educates students in all aspects. Conflict science, together with these subjects, teaches the relationship between the teacher and the student, etiquette, mutual understanding, respect, honor between the teacher and the student, and conflict resolution skills. Being demanding and fair is one of the professional and ethical qualities of a teacher, who is a subject of pedagogical conflict. A teacher must first of all be demanding of himself, so that his demands on the child will be appropriate and effective. Demandingness of the teacher should be related to fairness. At the same time, if the teacher's fairness is considered a teacher's moral quality, on the other hand, it is a criterion for evaluating the educational impact on students. The teacher is also required to be fair when evaluating the student's knowledge and behavior. The teacher is responsible and has the responsibility to educate the child as a well-rounded person. Only when the pedagogue works in compliance with the above, there will be no conflict between the teacher and the students.

The concept of pedagogical conflict. Pedagogical conflict is problems, arguments, disagreements between the teacher and the student, the teacher should prevent these problems, not allow them to occur, and find a solution to these problems.

One of the main reasons for pedagogical conflicts is that in the system of communication in the pedagogical process, the relationship between the teacher and the student occupies a large place. The teacher is the main figure in the pedagogical process. The teacher showed self-sacrifice in pedagogic work, performed his duty as a teacher at a high level, imparted knowledge to the children, and gained prestige and respect for the fact that he was able to instill the light of honesty, beauty, and manners into his heart, and was polite to the student.

Unfortunately, not all teachers have the right experience, sufficient knowledge and skills. Some of them are distinguished by not being able to give enough knowledge to the students, and some of them do not find a way to satisfy the student, and some of them are distinguished by rude treatment and hurting the student with inappropriate language.

Such pedagogues have a negative impact on the education of young people, the development of their knowledge and morals. In particular, it reaches the level of elementary classes that will adversely affect their future. As a result, students and young people do not strive for mature goals and goals in the future, and do not envy the honorable profession of a teacher. Such education and treatment do not correspond to universal national and moral norms in society.

In the pedagogical process, the nature of students is so complex that in order to form it correctly, the teacher needs to have high qualifications, strong knowledge, and mature experience. Some coaches believe that it is right to abuse and even beat students who do not meet their requirements in order to educate them. He thinks that if he does this, the student will be properly formed. Such situations can often occur among children living in unhealthy families with difficult upbringing. Therefore, it is necessary to study the living environment of each student based on his family situation. In the system of communication in the pedagogical process, the interaction between the teacher and the student takes a place. The teacher is the main figure, the leader in the pedagogical process. He is entrusted with the task of teaching and educating the young generation. The teacher-pedagogue showed dedication in his work, performed his duties as a teacher at a high level, imparted knowledge to children, instilled in them the light of honesty, beauty, truth, decency and morality, and gained such a reputation for being courteous. . I cite the following words of our first president I.A. Karimov as an example: "The fate of development is decided by spiritually mature people. Technical knowledge - the ability to master complex technology must go together

with mental maturity and independent thinking. Intellectual intelligence and spiritual potential are the two wings of an enlightened person." Therefore, first of all, it is necessary for the pedagogue-teacher to take into account the character and behavior of the student. Even encouraging students in some cases does not hurt. Forming the student's interest, encouraging him according to his favorite subject, for example, if there is a student who did not come to class due to family circumstances, or a student who did not prepare for class due to illness, it is permissible to treat them accordingly. Another example is that a student may miss a physical education class due to a weak leg, or be inactive in a literature class due to a headache. In such situations, it is appropriate to teach each student individually. Unfortunately, this cannot be said about all teachers. There are also those who, with their rude behavior, discourage the child from reading and hurt his tongue inappropriately.

There are many examples of this in pedagogical practice. Such they have a negative impact on the education of young people and their morals. They cause damage to educational work that is difficult to repair. As a result, conflicts arise between the teacher and the student. Ethical norms related to the formation and upbringing of a perfect creative personality are expressed in pedagogical ethics. One of the conditions for having a positive influence on the student is the unity of the demands placed on him. This rule has been tested and justified in pedagogical practice. The results of the interviews conducted by teachers with students indicate that, along with polite teachers, there are also teachers who beat and shout at children indiscriminately. Such treatment does not correspond to universal and national moral norms accepted in the society. Such teachers cannot gain respect among children.

In the pedagogical process, in the process of education, the nature of people is so complicated that the teacher sometimes has to be rude whether he wants to or not. When the student does not fulfill the reasonable demands of the teacher, he loses his temper. The teacher considers his demands, even rudeness, to be good for the child, because he believes that he is doing this to educate the child, to guide him in the right direction, and to raise him to be a good person.

Abdulla Awlani's deeply meaningful words that "Education for us is a matter of either life or death, or salvation - or destruction, or happiness - or disaster" are consistent with our expressed opinion. Such situations often occur in the process of dealing with a child who is difficult to educate. It should not be forgotten that such a child usually comes from an unhealthy family. A child may be a victim of a bad environment in the family. Experienced pedagogues understand the complexity of working and dealing with a child who is difficult to educate, at the same time, they need human love, they also emphasize that they need politeness and attention, and the need to be tolerant, patient, and forgiving towards such people. As a result of some accidental behavior of the teacher, the opinion of the students about him can have a negative effect on the educational process and complicate the work of the teacher.

The teacher sometimes has disagreements with the students about work or personal matters. The student is critical of the assessment of others. That is the reason for the resentment and hesitation in his mood. Accidental success or encouragement from adults causes the child to overestimate himself and overconfidence. On the other hand, accidental failure can make a child lack confidence in his own strength, increase the feeling of hesitance, lack of courage and shyness. Therefore, the relationship of teachers and educators with children requires special delicacy.

The concept of pedagogical conflict. Pedagogical conflict is a disagreement between a teacher and a student.

A number of signs of pedagogical conflicts are:

- a) Crisis;
- b) Misunderstanding;
- c) An unexpected event;
- d) Tension;
- e) Inconvenience;
- f) Internal or external anxiety;
- g) Fear that is difficult to get rid of.

Factors causing pedagogical conflicts:

- I. Information factor;
- II. Attitude factor;
- III. Behavioral factor.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, we quote the following opinion from the works of the great Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Kominesky: "Teaching is higher than any other profession." Sometimes one person may not be able to educate one child, but a teacher teaches children science and manners, and experiences these hardships himself. That is why it is worth taking care of the teacher. It is necessary for a modern teacher to know and prevent the interaction between students, the use of social psychological relations, both in social psychology and in pedagogy. The future pedagogue should get acquainted with the foundations of pedagogical conflicts, that is, understand the causes of such conflicts, and at the same time, he should be able to widely apply theoretical knowledge about the methods of preventing and eliminating various conflicts in practice. Therefore, high knowledge, experience, dedication to their profession and skills are required from future pedagogues.

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